

1 **Design and kinetic optimization of a 3D-printed packed bed reactor for high-volume**
2 **continuous hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds and simultaneous production of**
3 **aromatic amines**

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13 **Abstract**

14 This study addresses the environmental risks associated with nitroaromatic compounds (NACs), widely
15 used in industrial processes but recognized as pollutants due to their persistence and toxicity. While
16 NACs are conventionally reduced to aromatic amines in batch processes, such methods present
17 challenges for large-scale operations due to inefficiencies and safety concerns. Here, we introduce a
18 flow-mode process utilizing a 3D-printed packed bed reactor (PBR) integrated with a rhenium-based
19 heterogeneous catalyst for continuous NACs hydrogenation. The breakthrough analysis highlighted the
20 superior capacity of the rhenium-loaded catalyst, achieving a sustained reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-
21 NP) over 1200 bed volumes (BVs) with no detectable breakthrough,. Kinetic modeling revealed high
22 reaction rates, with pseudo-first-order rate constants of 0.97 s⁻¹ for 4-NP and 0.36 s⁻¹ for 2,4,6-
23 trinitrophenol (2,4,6-TNP), significantly exceeding rates observed for nitrobenzene (NB) (0.11 s⁻¹).
24 Additionally, optimized process parameters enabled a flow rate of up to 37 BVs min⁻¹ for complete NAC
25 conversion, yielding a reactor capable of high-throughput operation. This work demonstrates that the
26 PBR, not only facilitates efficient waste stream remediation but also enables continuous extraction of
27 valuable fine chemicals, offering a scalable solution.

28 **Keywords:** rhenium; nitroaromatic; reaction kinetics; hydrogenation

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31

32 1. Introduction

33 Nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) are among the most critical industrial intermediates, playing a
34 key role in the production of various products, including rubber additives, perfumes, dyes [1-3],
35 polyurethanes, explosives, agrochemicals, pharmaceuticals [4], and many other organic chemicals [5].
36 These examples highlight only a fraction of the significance of NACs, which, due to their unique
37 properties, have become the largest class of chemicals utilized on an industrial scale [4, 5]. Given their
38 extensive use across multiple industries, NACs can easily contaminate water through direct discharge
39 or leaching, accumulate in soil via adsorption, or be released into the air through emissions such as
40 exhaust gases [6]. Due to their persistent nature, NACs tend to accumulate over time, posing significant
41 risks to ecosystems and human health [7].

42 While stricter control over explosive materials, pesticides, and the disposal of industrial waste
43 can help manage the environmental risks associated with NACs, a more effective and sustainable
44 alternative is to develop methods that allow for the recycling and reuse of these compounds within a
45 circular economy [8]. A key strategy is the direct reduction of $-\text{NO}_2$ groups to $-\text{NH}_2$, which offers
46 significant potential by transforming discarded NACs into intermediates for producing aromatic amines.
47 These amines are vital in the creation of photographic materials, corrosion inhibitors, polymers,
48 herbicides, dyes, and pharmaceuticals. Of particular importance, aromatic amines are fundamental in
49 the large-scale production of key pharmaceuticals, such as paracetamol, ibuprofen, acetaminophen (an
50 aspirin alternative), as well as antiandrogens like bicalutamide and nilutamide, linezolid (an antibiotic
51 for multidrug-resistant Gram-positive bacteria), and fosamprenavir (an anti-HIV medication that has
52 also shown promise in treating COVID-19) [9-12].

53 Traditionally, NACs are reduced to their corresponding amines using chemical processes that
54 are scalable from laboratory to industrial levels. The resulting amines are less toxic and serve as valuable
55 intermediates in the production of dyes, pharmaceuticals, photographic chemicals, explosives, corrosion
56 inhibitors, polymers, and rubber additives [13, 14]. Typically, these reduction methods are performed in
57 batch processes, where all reactants are introduced into a reactor, and after a set period, the products are
58 extracted. This cycle is then repeated. While batch processes offer certain advantages, such as simplicity
59 and the ability to control reaction parameters effectively, they also have limitations [4]. There are several
60 well-known batch reduction techniques for NACs, including catalytic hydrogenation [15],
61 metal/hydronium (H_3O^+) ion reduction [16], sulfide reductions [17], and reductive alkylation (Leuckart
62 Reaction) [18]. These “conventional” approaches are beneficial for optimizing yield due to the ease of
63 adjusting reaction conditions. However, they become less efficient in high-volume operations, where
64 frequent cleaning between batches and the complex handling of acids and reagents are required. This is
65 especially challenging when working with large quantities of NACs at elevated pressures and
66 temperatures, raising concerns about operational safety [19].

67 Flow-mode processes for the hydrogenation of NACs present several advantages over
68 traditional batch methods. In addition to continuous operation, they offer higher yields, reduced

69 downtime, enhanced automation, and improved control and safety [20, 21]. Notably, these processes
70 also have the potential to convert waste streams containing NACs into valuable aromatic amines, making
71 them a promising approach for the catalytic extraction of these fine chemicals from various waste
72 sources. However, the majority of existing research focuses on batch reduction methods, primarily on
73 the development of novel catalytic materials [22-26]. In this context, within the present study we propose
74 a new flow-mode process aimed at the continuous NACs reduction.

75 The aim of this work is to design and produce a 3D-printed packed bed reactor (PBR) for the
76 continuous hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs), with a focus on maximizing both
77 process efficiency and the simultaneous production of valuable aromatic amines. This novel approach
78 of treating NACs containing streams as a rich source of aromatic amines was implemented by
79 incorporating rhenium nanoparticles-based heterogeneous catalyst. As such, this research seeks to
80 address the limitations of traditional batch processes and leverage the advantages of flow-mode systems
81 for high-volume NAC processing. The study not only establishes the catalytic capacity of the reactor for
82 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) reduction but also extends the kinetic modeling to other nitroaromatics to identify
83 optimal operating conditions. The successful validation of these conditions in a continuous process
84 demonstrates the reactor's potential for large-scale NAC remediation and fine chemical recovery,
85 highlighting its industrial relevance.

86 **2. Materials and methods**

87 **2.1. Reagents and materials**

88 All of the materials used for the production of packed bed reactor (PBR) were acquired from
89 Formlabs (MA, USA) *via*. CAD Expert (Poland) distribution. These include building platforms for 3D
90 printer, resin tanks as well as Clear v4 photocurable resin. The PBR was sealed after assembly with 3D
91 printed threads. All of the reagents used for the heterogeneous catalyst synthesis as well as research on
92 the flow-mode catalytic process were acquired from Merck (branch Poland). All other reagents named
93 in this manuscript were purchased in Avantor Performance Materials Ltd. (Poland). The chemicals were
94 of analytical grade or better and were used as received. Merck Milipore system was used to prepare
95 reverse osmosis water that was used through all the experiments.

96 The heterogeneous catalyst was synthesized using a procedure previously described in the reference
97 cited under number [27]. Briefly, a commercial, chloromethylated styrene-co-divinylbenzene matrices
98 (Purolite Ltd. Branch Poland, Gdynia, Poland) of expanded gel or mesoporous structures were modified
99 using bis(3-aminopropyl)amine (BAPA). Then, rhenium (Re) active sites were loaded onto the so-
100 prepared polymers. It was done by contacting the BAPA-functionalized anion exchange resins with
101 a solution containing ReO_4^- ($1000 \text{ mg Re L}^{-1}$). After 48 hours, the Re-loaded resins were washed with
102 water, and then placed in 1 L of water to initiate the process of in-situ reduction of Re(VII) on BAPA
103 functionalities [27]. The catalysts, coded as GM#Re (gel-matrix) and MP#Re (mesoporous matrix) were
104 then used in swollen form without any additional treatment.

2.2. Analyses and instrumentation

The surface composition of the heterogeneous catalyst was determined using a SPECS PHOIBOS-100 X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (XPS). Analyzes were performed with a hemispherical spectrometer, equipped with a Mg X-ray source (1253.6 eV) operating at 250 W for high-resolution spectra acquisition. The obtained spectra were processed using SPECLAB 2 and CasaXPS version 2.19 software, employing a Gaussian-Lorentzian curve fit and a Shirley baseline. The C 1s peak at 284.8 eV served as the reference point. To prevent differential charging on the sample surfaces, an electron flood gun was used. The catalysts' porosity was estimated using ASAP 2020 Plus Automatic Physisorption Analyzer (Micrometrics, GA, USA). Prior the analysis the samples were outgassed at 60 °C for 24 h. The acquired low temperature N₂ adsorption-desorption data were then re-calculated to the surface areas using Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) theory.

Catalytic reaction rates were monitored using a SPECORD 210 PLUS UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Analytik-Jena, Jena, Germany), with spectra recorded across the 200–600 nm range at a resolution of 1 nm.

2.3. Flow-mode process design and optimization

The process of continuous flow-mode hydrogenation of NACs was developed with the aid of stereolithographic 3D printing technology. For this purpose, PBR was designed in Autodesk Inventor Professional 2025 software provided under the license issued for the Wroclaw University of Science and Technology. Then, all CAD designs were exported to *.stl files that were then optimized and prepared for production using Formlabs (MA, USA) PreForm 3.41.0 software. After this, the column displayed in **Figure 1a** was printed on Formlabs Form3 3D printer using using Clear v4 (Formlabs) photocurable resin. Then, the final product was washed in isopropanol with the aid of FormWash (Formlabs) device, and then cured under UV light at 60 °C using FormCure (Formlabs) UV oven.

After this, the Re-loaded catalysts GM_Re or MP_Re (catalyst Bed Volume, BV=3.65 mL) were packed into PBR (total volume of PBR: 4.2 mL), and the column was closed through designed and produced thread joints. The so-prepared column was then set into the process setting as displayed in **Figure 1b**. The setup included containers with NACs solutions (0.1 mmol L⁻¹) and ice-cooled NaBH₄ (0.1 mol L⁻¹). These reagents were then transferred to the PBR using Masterflex MFLX07522-30-EU peristaltic pumps applying flow rates that ensured 100-fold molar excess of NaBH₄ in respect to NACs. In this way, depending on a test, the flow rate through the PBR was varied between 1 and 80 mL min⁻¹, which corresponds to 0.27-22 BVs min⁻¹. The PBR outflows were then collected in 20 mL test tubes using Büchi B-684 (Switzerland) fraction collector, and analyzed using UV-Vis spectrophotometry by recording spectra in the range of 200-600 nm.

138

139 **Figure 1.** (a) Packed bed reactor 3D design; (b) research setup for the process optimization. (1) NACs, (2)

140 ice-cooled NaBH₄, (3) peristaltic pumps, (4) PBR, (5) fraction collector.

141 The spectra were used to estimate the absorbances of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP, 400 nm),

142 Nitrobenzene (NB, 275 nm), 2-nitroaniline (2-NA, 410 nm), 4-nitroaniline (4-NA, 380 nm), and 2,4,6-

143 trinitrophenol (2,4,6-TNP, 390 nm). The collected absorbances in the PBR outflows (A_v) were then set

144 with initial absorbance of tested NACs (A_0). Then, the A_v/A_0 ratios were set in A_v/A_0 - f (BVs) graphs to
145 determine PBR breakthrough curves that allowed to determine PBR's catalytical capacity.

146 The PBRs' kinetic modelling was carried out in the following way. NACs and NaBH_4 solutions
147 were pumped through the PBR with the flow rates ranging from 1-80 mL min^{-1} . The collected outflows
148 were analyzed using UV-Vis, and the flow rates were re-calculated to reagents-catalytical bed space time
149 (τ) that was considered equal to reaction time (t). Because the hydrogenation reaction carried out in the
150 present scenario resulted in generation of H_2 gas, the catalytical bed was constantly mixed through the
151 process. Hence, the reaction at the given t was considered in the terms of BATCH model in respect to
152 reagents accumulation, and the PBR's kinetics modelling was done in the following way. First, it was
153 assumed that the ratio of registered absorbances is equal to the corresponding 4-NP concentrations ratios
154 which gave the differential kinetic equation (1):

$$155 \quad \frac{dA}{dt} = -kA \quad (1)$$

156 That after integration gives the accumulation model (2):

$$157 \quad \ln\left(\frac{A_0}{A_v}\right) = kt$$

158 Based on these, the first order kinetics were plotted as $\ln(A_0/A_v) = f(t)$ and the flow-mode process
159 rate constants ($k_{\text{fm}}, \text{s}^{-1}$) were taken from the slope of the above-mentioned plots.

160 3. Results and discussion

161 3.1. PBR's catalytical "capacity"

162 In the first stage of the process optimization, two columns loaded with either GM#Re or MP#Re
163 heterogenous catalysts were prepared. Both of these, were aligned in the setup (**Figure 1b**), and the 4-
164 NP together with NaBH_4 were dosed to the system with the flow rate set at 1 mL min^{-1} . The column
165 effluent was collected using fraction collector, and the UV-Vis spectra were recorded. **Figure 2** displays
166 UV-Vis spectra as well as PBR's breakthrough curves for the process.

167

168 **Figure 2.** PBR breakthrough and UV-Vis spectra of the effluents recorded for the continuous flow mode
 169 hydrogenation of 4-NP carried out over (A) GM#Re (1200 BVs) and (B) MP#Re (430 BVs) catalysts.
 170 $C_{4-NP}=0.1 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$, $C_{NaBH_4}=0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, 4-NP flow rate: 0.91 mL min^{-1} , $NaBH_4$ flow rate: 0.09 mL min^{-1} ;
 171 $BV=3.65 \text{ mL}$

172 Based on the data presented in **Figure 2**, the PBR loaded with both of the catalysts is able to
 173 process high quantities of 4-NP under the operational conditions. PBR loaded with GM#Re processed
 174 outstanding 1200 BVs of 4-NP. This value corresponds to 4300 mL of 4-NP solution, and what must be
 175 noticed, even though, no column breakthrough was observed (**Figure 2A**). In the case of MP#Re
 176 catalytical bed, the PBR enables hydrogenation of 330 BVs before a 4-NP appears in the column
 177 effluent. This value corresponds to the 1200 mL of 4-NP processed in the present setup. After this, a
 178 rapid column breakthrough is observed and the PBR does not serve its function anymore (**Figure 2B**).

179 One of the most remarkable outcomes of this flow-based technology is its dual functionality in
 180 processing 4-NP (**Figure 2A**). First, the system demonstrated exceptional capacity for high-volume
 181 treatment, with no breakthrough of 4-NP detected even after 1200 bed volumes (BVs), highlighting its
 182 impressive efficiency. More importantly, the effluents contained no trace of 4-NP throughout the entire
 183 test (**Figure 2A**). Instead, distinct bands corresponding to 4-aminophenol, the desired reduction product,
 184 emerged, signifying a successful and continuous conversion. This underscores the system's potential to
 185 function not only as an efficient waste treatment solution but also as a catalytic-extraction process
 186 capable of producing valuable fine chemicals, such as aromatic amines, from industrial waste streams.
 187 Similar effect could be observed in the case of PBR loaded with MP#Re (**Figure 2B**). The difference is
 188 however, that the breakthrough was observed soon when compared to the first PBR (**Figure 2A**).

189 Despite GM#Re catalytical bed was still functioning, due to the very large quantity of reagents
 190 processed, the test was stopped. The data clearly indicates that PBR with GM#Re is superior towards
 191 PBR with MP#Re catalytical bed. Hence, the first one was selected for further optimizations. However,
 192 before doing so, it was needed to explain, why both of these catalysts behave so differently.

193 3.2. Heterogeneous catalysts characteristics

194 The basis for this new flow-mode technology of NACs reduction is the catalytic material that has been
195 previously developed by our research team [27-29]. To confirm similar phase composition and
196 morphology, the present GM#Re sample was subjected to the XPS analysis. **Figure 3** displays Re 4f
197 spectra of along with catalyst profile analysis.

198

199 **Figure 3.** XPS spectra of GM#Re catalyst. **(A)** Re 4f envelope with its deconvolution ; **(B)** QUASES™
200 ‘Analyze’ modeled peaks of analyzed catalyst surface:, N 1s, and Re 4f using Mg K α source.

201 The deconvolution of the C 1s spectrum (**Figure S1**) accurately reflects the polymer matrix
202 structure. The ratios of C=C to C–C and C=C to C–N bonds are both 0.5. The latter ratio indicates that
203 the polymer matrices have undergone complete modification, as is also evidenced by the absence of Cl
204 in the XPS spectra. Based on the deconvolution of the Re 4f spectrum (**Figure 3A**), the dominant form
205 of Re in the catalyst is Re(IV) (62%), with 32% being higher oxides, including Re(VII), and 6%
206 representing Re(0). The structure of the outermost layer of the Re-loaded catalyst was modeled using
207 QUASES software [30] (**Figure 3B**). In the first step, the thickness of the adventitious carbon layer was
208 determined by analyzing the N 1s region using the QUASES-Tougard Analysis program with Mg K α
209 excitation. The experimental data were fitted using a 'buried layer' model, assuming that 'polymeric
210 nitrogen' (bulk nitrogen) is covered by contamination carbon. This profile models the energy loss of
211 photoelectrons emitted from atoms within a homogeneous layer as they pass through an overlying
212 material of different composition. The contamination layer's thickness was estimated to be
213 approximately 0.8-1.0 nm. In the next step, the depth to which the Re oxide phase penetrated the polymer
214 surface was determined. The best fit for the Re 4f spectrum was again obtained using the 'buried layer'
215 model (**Figure 3B**), showing that rhenium is present in a layer extending from about 0.8 to 7 nm, thus
216 limiting the maximum particle size of Re to around 7 nm.

217 This conclusion is also supported by high resolution transmission electron microscopy image
218 (**Figure S2**) that reveal the same morphology of Re active sites as in the case of previous samples [27-
219 29]. Namely, Re formed particularly small, highly dispersed nanostructures with a morphology of locally
220 grouped, catalytically active “apparent nanoparticles” consisting of several Re atoms.

221 Because of these observations, and the similarities between present and past samples [27-29] it may
222 be stated that the Re-active species morphology does not affect the catalytical activity of heterogenous
223 catalyst. If so, based on already gained experience, the catalytic activity depends on the synergistic effect
224 between Re and amino functionalities used for the reduction and capping of ReO_4^- [27]. In the present
225 case however, the applied amino functionality is the same in both of the catalysts. This must mean, that
226 the only aspect these samples differ, namely, morphology of the polymeric matrix, must had play a role
227 in the catalysts behavior.

228 The catalysts GM#Re and MP#Re were based on expanded-gel structure, and mesoporous structure
229 matrices, respectively. Based on the BET analysis, the GM#Re catalyst contained no porosity, while
230 MP#Re revealed approximate surface area of $13 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ with pore range fitting in the range of 1.97-50.15
231 nm (**Figure S3**). This confirmed, on the one hand, its mesoporous structure, and on the other hand,
232 indicated that the porosity of the MP#Re may be attributed to the surface roughness. Because of the
233 latter one, it is unlikely that the catalyst suffered diffusion limitations inside the polymeric network but
234 rather tend to adsorb 4-NP and thus to getting poisoned. The confirmation for this conclusion is the
235 observation that unlike the GM#Re, the MP#Re became the same color as 4-NP solution during the
236 process (**Figure S4**), and the PBR breakthrough progress could be observed with a bare eye.

237 **3.3. Optimization of process operating parameters**

238 Based on the results, the PBR loaded with GM#Re catalyst was selected for further tests. As
239 displayed in **Figure 2A**, and discussed above, the GM#Re catalytical bed revealed not only outstanding
240 ability to process high volumes of 4-NP but also enabled achieving additional effect of catalytically-
241 driven 4-aminophenol extraction. This phenomenon could be used to propose a new technology of
242 circular production of this fine chemical product. Because of this, in the next stage of research, the
243 developed PBR-based setup was optimized to find best suited process operating conditions. For this
244 purpose, the stream of 4-NP and NaBH_4 was introduced into PBR with flow rate ranging from 1 to 80
245 mL min^{-1} . In addition to 4-NP, streams consisting of NB, 2-NA, 4-NA, and 2,4,6-TNP, were used as
246 well. **Figure 4** displays the $A_v/A_0=f(\tau)$ plots for the catalytic hydrogenations of 4-NP, NB, 2-NA, 4-NA,
247 and 2,4,6-TNP.

248

249 **Figure 4.** Absorbance vs. space time plots and first order kinetics for the hydrogenations of (A) 4-NP, (B) NB,
 250 (C) 2-NA, (D) 4-NA, and (E) 2,4,6-TNP. (F) BVs vs. flow rate plots for theoretical 100% and 80% yields of 4-
 251 NP hydrogenation

252 The main aim of this test was to find the PBR's breakthrough profile in the function of reagents
253 stream space time with catalytic bed. The so-obtained profiles (**Figure 4**) demonstrate these
254 breakthroughs. Based on the data collected, the catalytical reductions of NACs, may be considered in
255 two steps. The first one, considered as "longer" space times (smaller flow rates) ensures ~100% of NACs
256 conversions. The second one, considered as "shorter" space times (greater flow rates), demonstrates the
257 actual PBR's breakthrough (**Figure 4**). Both of these reactions steps were approximated, and maximum
258 space times at which 100% NACs hydrogenation occurs were determined. Based on this, the least space
259 time needed to fully convert 4-NP, NB, 2-NA, 4-NA and 2,4,6-TNP are 5.9, 12.9, 14.5, 8.2 and 5.9
260 seconds, respectively. These values correspond to the flow rates for 4-NP: 38 BVs min⁻¹, NB: 17 BVs
261 min⁻¹, 2-NA: 15 BVs min⁻¹, 4-NA: 27 BVs min⁻¹ and 2,4,6-TNP: 37 BVs min⁻¹. Simultaneously, the
262 observed PBRs' breakthroughs allowed to plot $\ln(A_v/A_0)$ vs. t functions, namely, first order kinetics for
263 each tested PBR. Based on these, the flow mode process rate constants (k_{fm}) ranged from 0.11 to 0.93 s⁻¹
264 ¹, and the PBR's activity can be arranged in the following order 4-NP>2,4,6-TNP>4-NA>2-NA>NB
265 (**Figure 4A-E**). This outcome is interesting, because in past reports [27, 31], the greater number of –
266 NO₂ groups in a single NAC molecule is, the lower rate constants should be observed. In the present
267 scenario however, the hydrogenation 2,4,6-TNP, characterized by the presence of three –NO₂ groups
268 revealed much greater k_{fm} (0.36 s⁻¹, **Figure 4E**) than k_{fm} recorded for the NB characterized by one –
269 NO₂ group (0.11 s⁻¹, **Figure 4B**), and was second-greatest after 4-NP reduction (0.97 s⁻¹, **Figure 4A**).
270 This may suggest, that in the flow mode process there may be an additional influence of polymeric
271 matrix used as a support for Re-loaded catalyst. It has been previously suggested that the vinyl-based
272 copolymers reveal great affinity for phenolic species [32]. The present results are consistent with this
273 statement, as generally the k_{fm} values may be grouped as follows
274 nitrophenols>nitroanilines>nitrobenzenes (**Figure 4**). This conclusion opens a path for further
275 optimizations related to the selection of catalysts' matrices best suited to particular applications.

276 The flow-mode process kinetics modelling allowed to estimate a theoretical PBR behavior in the
277 function of flow rate, namely, process efficiency. **Figure 4F** displays modelled relation between
278 theoretical BVs of catalysts in the function of predicted flow rate for 100% and 80% yields of 4-NP
279 conversions, respectively. As can be seen (**Figure 4F**), to carry out the process of 4-NP hydrogenation
280 with an efficiency of 1000 L min⁻¹, a PBR containing 62 L of GM#Re catalysts would be required to
281 achieve complete 4-NP conversion, and just 27 L of GM#Re if 80% conversion would be enough. Based
282 on these results and considerations, the proposed PBR could enable flow-mode NACs hydrogenation
283 that might be optimized towards effective production of aromatic amines with "programmable" purity.

284 3.4. Process validation

285 The optimized PBR was validated in the 4-NP reduction under determined optimal conditions. To do so,
286 a PBR loaded with 3.65 mL of GM#Re catalyst was set, and the reaction mixture was passed through
287 the column applying flow rate of 37 mL min⁻¹ (10 BVs min⁻¹, $\tau=5.9$ s). These flow rates were determined

288 as the maximum at which 100% conversion of 4-NP is achieved (see section 3.3 for details). The process
289 was carried out until 1340 BVs of PBR effluent was collected, and then the process was evaluated. The
290 **Figure 5** displays breakthrough curves of the process with UV-Vis spectra, recorded for the collected
291 effluents.

292

293 **Figure 5.** 4-NP hydrogenation breakthrough curve and PBR's effluent UV-Vis spectra recorded for the process
294 carried out under process parameters optimized towards maximum flow rates and 100% 4-NP conversion.
295 $C_{4\text{-NP}}=0.1 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$, $C_{\text{NaBH}_4}=0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, 4-NP flow rate: $33.64 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$, NaBH_4 flow rate: 3.36 mL min^{-1} ;
296 $\text{BV}=3.65 \text{ mL}$

297 As can be seen in **Figure 5**, the process was successfully validated. The applied conditions ensured
298 regents-catalytical bed space time of 5.9 s, and within these conditions the PBR successfully reduced 4-
299 NP and produced 4-AP (**Figure 5**). The process proceeded undisturbed until 1100 BVs has passed
300 through the column. After this, a sharp breakthrough was observed, and the PBR immediately lost its
301 catalytic activity. It must be noted, that no Re leaching was observed during the process, hence it may
302 be estimated that the lost of catalytic activity must had been related to the oxidation of catalyst's active
303 sites, as it was observed before [27]. Nevertheless, the 1100 BVs of 4-NP solution that the PBR was able
304 to process may be considered as impressive. To put it into the perspective, if a PBR had the volume of
305 200 L, the amount of 4-NP solution it could theoretically process before loosing its catalytic activity is
306 220 m^3 . Simultaneously, it must be noted that if the process was carried out at lower flow rates (greater
307 space times) the PBR catalytic activity could last longer, as when the process was carried out initially,
308 we did not reach PBR's breakthrough even after processing 1200 BVs of the 4-NP solution (see section
309 3.1 for details).

310 4. Conclusion

311 This study successfully demonstrates the potential of a 3D-printed packed bed reactor (PBR)
312 incorporating rhenium (Re) catalysts for the efficient, continuous reduction of nitroaromatic compounds
313 (NACs). Our findings reveal that the PBR loaded with GM#Re catalysts exhibits a superior capacity for
314 high-volume treatment, processing up to 1200 bed volumes of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) without any
315 breakthrough, thereby underscoring its robustness in large-scale applications. The continuous flow
316 process not only achieves effective NAC removal but also facilitates the selective production of valuable
317 aromatic amines, such as 4-aminophenol, confirming the dual functionality of the system as both a waste
318 treatment and catalytic extraction process.

319 The distinct behavior observed between the GM#Re and MP#Re catalysts was analyzed with XPS
320 and electron microscopy confirming, that the Re phase penetrates the catalyst's polymer surface,
321 forming highly dispersed nanostructures with maximum particle sizes of 7 nm. These nanoscale Re sites,
322 combined with amino-functionalized supports, enhance the catalytic reduction efficiency, particularly
323 in the GM#Re-loaded PBR.

324 Detailed optimization of the reactor's kinetic parameters allowed to link the flow rates to find
325 optimal space time (τ) for maximum NACs conversion. Developed kinetic models for first-order
326 reactions, including the rate constants obtained through this modeling inform the reactor's catalytic
327 performance and highlight the critical role of flow rate adjustments in enhancing NACs processing
328 capacity. The optimized kinetics support continuous high-volume processing, facilitating seamless
329 transitions from lab-scale experiments to industrial applications.

330 This reactor system represents an innovative approach to flow-mode catalytic processes, promising
331 operational safety, higher automation, and improved control. The successful application of this
332 technology highlights its industrial relevance for continuous NAC remediation and the sustainable
333 recovery of fine chemicals, positioning it as a viable alternative to traditional, environmentally
334 unsustainable batch processes. Future work may focus on further optimizing the reactor's design and
335 exploring broader applications in environmental and chemical engineering contexts.

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341 **6. Data availability statement**

342 The data are stored under permanent identifier <https://doi.org/10.18150/KUPKUZ>

343 **7. Competing interests statement**

344 The authors declare no competing interests.

345 **8. Credit author contributions**

346 **PC:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data
347 Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project
348 administration, Funding acquisition. **WT:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – Review and Editing.
349 **DJB:** Investigation, Resources, Writing-Review and Editing

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